

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of metastasis to the skeletal system:**
2 **ERBB2.**

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7 We study breast cancer in humans as a model for understanding cancer as a system in its entirety and as
8 a life cycle, including cell of origin, transformation, subtype selection, biology and ecology of the primary
9 tumor, the tumor microenvironment, tumor immunology and surveillance, dissemination via the circulating
10 tumor cell, metastasis to the lymph nodes, and metastasis to distant sites. Metastasis is the major cause
11 of death from cancer and patients with breast cancer are at risk of developing one of four major
12 metastases to a distant site, which we argue lymph node metastasis is a precursor to (rather than simply a
13 reflection of): metastasis to the CNS (e.g., the brain), metastasis to the lungs, metastasis to the liver, and
14 metastasis to the skeletal system (bones) (1-5). We recently utilized whole transcriptome technologies to
15 define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer:
16 in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we utilize whole transcriptome
17 technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the bone metastases of humans with breast cancer,
18 comparing the bone metastatic transcriptome to the primary tumor transcriptome and to normal cells from
19 the breast. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its optimized therapeutic index: differential
20 expression and up-regulation upon metastasis to the bone, ERBB2, as a candidate therapeutic target for
21 the medical management of bone metastasis.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the skeletal system to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the bone metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: ERBB2.

Results

Figure 1: ERBB2 is differentially expressed in bone metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

- I. Bone metastases and normal mammary epithelial cells; human breast cancer.

n=3 normal mammary epithelial cells

n=3 bone metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_2352131	6.94e-11	-40.884593	15.884969	-3.7613646	ERBB2	241/40614	99.4

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal cells of the breast and in bone metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of erb-b2 receptor tyrosine kinase 2, encoded by *ERBB2* in metastasis to the skeletal system in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of ERBB2 changed more than 99% of the human bone metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 40,614 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of ERBB2 messenger RNA in bone metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of ERBB2 during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

Thus, differential and increased expression of ERBB2 defines the bone metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of ERBB2, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with bone metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of bone metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

References

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Methods

We utilized GSE55715 (Dataset 1) for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the skeletal system (bones) and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE121677 [Dataset 2] for target validation) using microarray and RNA-sequencing data (published) and R-based computational methods.